

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LAFAYETTE****FIRST NAME: LEV****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0% (excluding referenced quotations)

The author used the following software: LibreOffice 24.8.1.2 on Ubuntu Linux 20.4.6 LTS. Reviewed with MS-Word 365.

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7-11)
2. Punctuation and Spelling (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16-32)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41-48)
4. Style Guides and CMS Crib Sheet (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41-48)
5. Sample Corrections (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 65-72)

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK REVIEW

1) INTRODUCTION

The Euclid University coursepack is designed to provide “essential guidance for both international academics and professionals on the fundamentals of paper writing... this comprehensive module serves as a foundational resource, covering key aspects such as essay composition, punctuation, plagiarism avoidance, and adherence to style conventions” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 3). The first chapter provides an overview of essay writing, the second on punctuations [sic], the third on the differences between American and British English, the fourth on plagiarism, the fifth on style guides, followed by a CMS (Content Management System) “crib sheet”, a chapter on Latin abbreviations before concluding with sample corrections to a paper.

The following review addresses the overview of essay writing, a combined review of the punctuation and U.S. vs U.K. English chapters, the chapter on plagiarism, and the chapter on style guides, combined with a review of the CMS chapter, before analysing the sample correction chapter. The chapter on Latin abbreviations is not addressed as these are sufficiently commonly understood and are part of most English style guides with a high

level of consistency. A critical conclusion addresses the place of the coursepack within doctoral studies.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter starts with a definition: “Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7), although doctoral students in creative writing, for example, will note this is only partially true in some disciplines. This aside, the chapter illustrates the importance of establishing a research question, the tasks required to analyse it, and planning the research. According to the coursebook, research is conducted broadly but with a narrow focus on the content for material relevant to the research topic. In addition, thinking about writing should include creativity to broaden ideas and critical thinking to evaluate the substance of an argument (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 9). The essay structure follows a well-established “Introduction”, “Body”, and “Conclusion” approach with additional detail, but there is a helpful identification of how this process is reiterated on a micro-level with essay paragraphs (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10-11). This initial stage of preparation and writing of the first draft is followed by requirements, such as referencing, and helpful comments on editing and writing, such as suggestions to avoid generalisations and passive construction (e.g., passive constructions are to be avoided).

3) PUNCTUATION AND SPELLING

The chapter on punctuation starts with a seemingly unusual general recommendation, “use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 16), and then provides several examples of use, for example, the well-known use of apostrophes to indicate possession but not plurals, the difference in the use of the colon and semi-colon, the use of commas (the distinction between defining and non-defining clauses being especially notable), hyphens (do not use for new compound nouns or adjectival phrases), and the use of quotation marks (encapsulate quotes within quotes with single then double).

The following chapter compares and contrasts U.S. and U.K. English, beginning with a nascent sociology of the increasing dominance of the former in world English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25) before noting heteronymic, homophonic, and homonymic differences, along with a range of other differences in collective nouns, pluralised adjectives, and influences from other cultures. The writing of dates is quite a famous distinction between the two languages, with the additional recognition of the importance of the ISO-8601 standard (year, month, day). A notable example is the difference between encapsulated quotation marks where the examples given in this chapter for U.K. English differ from the example given in the previous chapter, which is standard for U.S. English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 31-32).

4) **PLAGIARISM**

Plagiarism is defined as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34) with some reasons provided on why this behaviour is unacceptable such ethics and academic consequences); other reasons could include the fact that employers will quickly discover incompetence, leading to a loss of income and damage to an institution’s reputation if plagiarism is accepted. The primary means to avoid plagiarism is to ensure proper citation of sources, whether through in-text citation of quotations or paraphrases; common knowledge does not need to be cited (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34-37). Referencing rules for the conclusion of texts are also provided for books, online works, and with footnote-style references. Curiously, an absolute prohibition on contractions is also provided in this chapter (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 39) when logically it should be in the chapter concerning punctuation or style; it is difficult to discern what this has to do with plagiarism or citation practices.

5) **STYLE GUIDES AND CMS CRIB SHEET**

There is an opening note that Euclid recommends the Chicago rules and U.S. English, but other international guides and U.K. English are acceptable (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41). For the former, this includes scholarly systems such as the American Psychological Association (APA), Modern Language Association (MLA), the Vancouver system, and the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). As is evident, style guides often focus on a particular range of academic disciplines. The introduction emphasises consistency: “Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41).

The Style Guide chapter is short, effectively two pages of written content. Most of the guide content is found in the “CMS Crib Sheet” chapter, which spans thirteen pages (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 44-57), although this usually refers to a single page. This aside, the chapter reiterates that the Chicago style is used by default and outlines several key features and implementation of this style, including abbreviations, capitalisation, compound words, italics and quotation marks, numbers, quotations, page formatting, footnotes, headers and lists, tables, endnotes and footnotes, and bibliographies. As can be expected, this is only a summary of the broader document (Turabian 2018); however, a thoroughly useful one that includes highlights significant variations from expected norms and changes, such as the use of American-standard dating format (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 48), itself notable as contrary to ISO standards and challenging to implement in computer operating systems.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS

The corrections to a sample paper chapter Cleenewerck & Gulma (2024, 65-72) illustrate an implementation of the concepts used in the coursepack, with the stated objectives of “understand how the instructor provides response” and “learn some of the dos and donts [sic] of writing a response paper.” It is observed that the coursepack here is ignoring its recommendations on apostrophe and contraction usage. Further, it is noted that the sample paper commentary does not match the template provided by Euclid University; for example, the template asks for the instructor’s last name only, whereas the commentary includes the title and last name. In both cases, the Boolean operative for the use of Zotero uses an exclusive OR statement when an AND would be more appropriate; it is possible to use Zotero and not use Zotero to insert references as some references could be entered manually, for example, due to an error in the application.

The comments on the sample paper use the limited method employed by M.S. Word and other word processing systems rather than a fully-fledged version control system (e.g., Git, Subversion). The content of the comments is limited to grammatical and spelling mistakes, such as incorrect use of plurals, incorrect referencing, and the overuse of passive constructions in sentences. Surprisingly, there is no commentary on the use of highly informal language throughout the sample and supposedly academic paper, such as a plethora of personal opinions, experiences, and statements using the “I” singular, first-person pronoun.

7) CONCLUSION

Orientation documents that warn students about matters such as plagiarism or a university CMS are common and welcomed, as are recommended style guides that help provide consistency and legibility in writing. However, A serious question is whether such guides should be part of the formal curriculum. It is certainly not the experience of this student, who has studied degrees at several universities across Australia, New Zealand, and the United Kingdom, where the expectation is that at the higher degree level, the student should review and understand such things in their own time and as part of their responsibility as an independent researcher.

Likewise, there is the issue of a constrained recommendation of a style guide; again, at the research level of higher education, there is an expectation that the student selects the style guide most appropriate to their discipline and preferences after researching for themselves why style guides are essential and should be followed. Whilst such matters are a matter for Euclid University’s procedures on curriculum development the broader andragogical issue (Purwati, 2022), of whether such scoping encourages intrinsic or extrinsic motivations, should not be ignored.

REFERENCES

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